

Laboratory tests of the MAVIS DNU Shack Hartmann Wavefront Sensor

Paolo Cerpelloni^{c,a,b}, Alessandro Ballone^{a,b}, Kalyan Kumar Radhakrishnan Santhakumari^{a,b}, Davide Greggio^{a,b}, Luca Marafatto^{a,b}, Matteo Aliverti^l, Oleksandra Rebrysh^{a,b}, Daniele Vassallo^{a,b}, Sylvain Cetre^d, David Barr^e, Gabriele Umbriaco^{h,i,b}, Elena Carolo^{a,b}, Remon van Gaalen^{c,a,b}, Lorenzo Merli^{a,b}, Maria Bergomi^{a,b}, Valentina Viotto^{a,b}, and François Rigaut^{f,g}

^aINAF Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Vicolo dell'Osservatorio 5, 35122, Padova, Italy

^bADaptive Optics National laboratory in Italy (ADONI)

^cDipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia “Galileo Galilei”, Università degli Studi di Padova, Vicolo dell'Osservatorio 3, 35122, Padova, Italy

^dWakea Consulting, Rue Joseph Bouchayer 4, Grenoble, France

^eCentre for Advanced Instrumentation, DH1 3LE, Durham University, UK

^fAustralian National University, Research School of Astronomy and Astrophysics, Advanced Instrumentation Technology Centre, Canberra, Australia

^gAstralis Instrumentation Consortium, Australia

^hDipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia “Augusto Righi” - Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna, via Piero Gobetti 93/2 - 40129, Bologna, Italy

ⁱINAF Osservatorio di Astrofisica e Scienza dello Spazio, Bologna

^lINAF Osservatorio Astronomico di Brera, Via Emilio Bianchi 46, I 23807, Merate, Italy

ABSTRACT

MAVIS (MCAO Assisted Visible Imager and Spectrograph) is the next generation VLT instrument. MAVIS will feed an Imager, an Integral Field Unit spectrograph, and a third port instrument. MAVIS will provide a wide field (30" x 30") adaptive optics correction allowing scientific observations in the visible wavelength regime using Multi-Conjugated Adaptive Optics technique. MAVIS is expected to start the Alignment, Integration and Test phase during 2027. The Adaptive Optics Module (AOM) of MAVIS provides the wide field correction using eight Sodium Laser Guide Stars and up to three Natural Guide Stars. The Non-Common Path Aberrations (NCPA) from the different channels have to be efficiently removed to ensure reasonable Strehl correction. To verify the residual Wavefront Error (WFE) close to the scientific instruments and for diagnostic purposes, MAVIS has a component onboard called the Diagnostic and NCPA Unit (DNU). The DNU consists of two identical cameras

Further author information:

Paolo Cerpelloni: E-mail: paolo.cerpelloni@inaf.it

mounted on a common linear stage. One camera will act as an on-axis pupil imager, and the second one is equipped with a multi-lenslet array and it works as an on-axis Shack-Hartmann Wavefront Sensor (WFS). This work focuses on laboratory tests to characterize the performance of the DNU Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor.

We tested the DNU WFS on a laboratory bench at the University of Padova simulating an optical configuration similar to that of MAVIS. The bench is equipped with an ALPAO 97-15 Deformable Mirror (DM) and a 4D interferometer (Phasecam 4030) so the aberrations introduced by the DM can be measured simultaneously by the DNU WFS and by the interferometer. We used the basic functionalities of the real time controller DAO4MATTO (Durham Adaptive Optics for Multi conjugated Adaptive Techniques Test Optics). DAO4MATTO is still in a very early development phase, with limited testing tools available, but its basic functionalities can already be used to reach our goals.

Keywords: MAVIS, PFR, DNU, Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor

1. INTRODUCTION

MAVIS (MCAO Assisted Visible Imager and Spectrograph) ([5, 4]) is the next generation Very Large Telescope (VLT) instrument. By utilizing the Multi-Conjugated Adaptive Optics (MCAO) technique, it will deliver a 30" x 30" wide-field correction for observations in the visible range between 370-935 nm. Positioned on the UT4 Nasmyth platform, MAVIS will be integrated with the existing Adaptive Optics Facility (AOF): the secondary deformable mirror and the laser guide stars facility (which is expanding from four to eight laser guide stars). The system targets a Strehl ratio of $\geq 8\%$ across its full field of view under standard Paranal turbulence conditions (0.83" seeing at 500 nm). MAVIS is equipped with a 4k x 4k Imager (7.3 mas per pixel) and an Integral Field Unit (IFU) with four spectral resolution modes. MAVIS, as the next general purpose instrument for the VLT, will combine high sensitivity imaging, spectroscopy, and high angular resolution at optical wavelengths enabling the instrument to address a diverse range of scientific questions, categorized into four primary themes: a) Emergence of Hubble sequence, b) Resolving galaxy contents, c) Star Clusters as mergers of galaxy evolution, and d) Birth, life and death of stars and planets. The full description of MAVIS science cases can be found in the MAVIS white book [3].

Istituto Nazionale di AstroFisica (INAF) is in charge of the MAVIS Adaptive Optics Module (AOM) [8, 2, 7]. The AOM provides a wide field correction using eight Sodium Laser Guide Stars and up to three Natural Guide Stars. One of the AOM modules is called the Diagnostic and NCPA Unit (DNU). As the name suggests, DNU is mainly used for diagnostic purposes. It has two modes - (1) on-axis pupil imager and (2) on-axis Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor (SH-WFS) that can measure the residual Wavefront Error (WFE) close to the scientific instruments, ideally measured after the Non-Common Path Aberrations (NCPA) correction. The DNU SH-WFS mode will act as a reliable, linear, on-axis, imager-independent way of measuring the residual aberrations. Additionally, this tool will be used during the Alignment, Integration and Test phase.

Fig. 1 shows the location of the DNU inside MAVIS. A selection mirror reflects in the on-axis beam towards the DNU. The beam first meets a circular field stop, followed by a folding mirror, and a collimating lens before reaching either the pupil imager camera or the SH-WFS camera unit, both of which are mounted on a linear stage. Figure 2 and Figure 3 show more details of the MAVIS DNU components.

The DNU SH-WFS is made by off-the-shelf components. Part of this work is to check if the assembly of these parts shows some differences with respect to the nominal design, and therefore make proper adjustments and design changes. The other part of the work is to characterize the DNU SH-WFS. In particular, our goal is to check the linearity of the SH slopes and to check if the setup is able to retrieve phase measurement of 20 nm, which is a requirement.

2. DNU SHACK-HARTMANN WAVEFRONT SENSOR ASSEMBLY

The DNU SH WFS assembly consists of a camera and a Multi-Lenslet Array (MLA). The camera is a BALLUFF BVS CA-GX0-0017ZG-110130-001 (Sony IMX425, 1600x1104 px, and pixel size of 9 μm). We tested the camera basic functionalities and verified the basic characteristics using darks and flat field frames.

We verified the mounting of the MLA and aligning it on the camera. The MLA is an OKO Technologies APO-Q-P200-F7.0 (633), size: 12mm x 12mm, with a focal length of 7 mm, and it is mounted with a C-mount ring adapter. To perform the alignment, we placed the camera perpendicular to a collimated beam coming from an interferometer. The correct focus position of the MLA, 7mm from the detector, was found checking the counts and the shape of the spot using the proprietary software of the camera. The MLA was moved in focus by rotating it inside the C-mount of the camera. When in focus, the counts should maximize and the spot should be circular.

DIAGNOSTIC and NCPA UNIT (DNU)

Figure 1. Left: CAD design of MAVIS with in blue the DNU components; Right: a zoom of the DNU components (a field stop, a folding mirror and a collimating lens and two cameras on a linear stage),

Figure 2. DNU field stop baffle, DNU field stop, DNU collimator doublet, DNU folding mirror.

We verified that the spots are all in the focus at the same time which confirms that the MLA is perpendicular to the detector plane. Also, ideally, we want to have the spots created by the MLA clocked well with the detector pixels. Fig 4 shows the MLA on the C-mount of the camera during the alignment process.

3. LABORATORY SETUP

The optical bench is located in the "Laboratorio di Eccellenza" at the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the University of Padova. The bench was set up to test the Durham Adaptive Optics (DAO) [1] Real Time Controller for the MATTO project [6]. In this context, we decided to mount the DNU SH-WFS to take advantage of the already working software and hardware setup. The optical configuration of the bench was designed trying to duplicate as much as possible on a smaller scale the optical properties of the DNU mounted on MAVIS. The main optical components of the bench are: a visible red laser source (633 nm), an ALPAO 97-15 Deformable Mirror (DM), a 4D interferometer and of course the DNU SH-WFS; see Fig. 5.

We can inject the light in the DNU SH-WFS in two ways, as marked in Fig. 5; a) with the laser source (orange line), which we used for the alignment of the optics, or b) with the interferometric beam itself. Option b is our go to option to compare the measurements between the DNU SH-WFS and the 4D interferometer. Referring to Fig. 5, the light is injected into the system by the interferometer, a first lens ($f=200$ mm) is used as the first component of a beam expander, a second lens ($f = 500$ mm) acts as second lens of a beam expander. We obtained a beam that allows us to sample the ALPAO 97-15 deformable mirror mounted after the second lens. After the reflection

Figure 3. DNU SH-WFS camera, DNU MLA, DNU pupil imager camera, DNU linear stage.

Figure 4. The MLA mounted on the camera during the alignment process.

on the DM, part of the light goes back to the interferometer and part of the light goes to DNU SH-WFS camera path. Here a lens ($f=300\text{mm}$) collimates the beam and the MLA is mounted in a position that is conjugated with the ALPAO 97-15 mirror. The two lenses: one in the SH path and the other one in the interferometer path are the only two components that differ between the two paths. These can be the sources of NCPA in the our setup.

We controlled all the components with the DAO interface. Through DAO workstation we control the DM, the DNU SH-WFS camera settings, the interferometer acquisition frame sequence, and closing and opening the loop. Table 1 tabulates the optics used for our setup.

4. LABORATORY TESTS

We calculated the best possible flat DM shape we could reach with our setup. To do so we closed the loop with the DNU SH-WFS. We saved the new flat DM shape.

We used this flat DM shape together with the interferometer to calibrate the injected amplitude modes commands on the mirror. In this way we had a 1:1 relation between the amplitude of the command we gave to the DM and the interferometer readings. Knowing the exact amplitude of the command helped to compare the aberrations reconstructed by the DNU SH-WFS. We sent commands to the DM. We measured the aberrations using both SH-WFS and interferometer. The linearity of the DM commands is also checked in the process for the first 16th Zernike modes from 150 nm to -150 nm at steps of 20 nm, see Fig 6.

Figure 5. The dashed red line is the interferometer path, the orange dashed line is the laser source path, the brown dashed line is the common path and the green dashed line is the DNU SH-WFS path. The figure shows also the positions of the lenses used in the setup.

Table 1. The optics used on the optical setup.

Type	Model	Focal Length	Diameter	Location
Singlet	Melles Griot - 01LDX341	200 mm	1 inch	Interferometer path
Cube beam splitter	Newport - 10BC16NP.4	-	-	
Cube beam splitter	Thorlabs - BS014	-	-	
Singlet	Thorlabs - LB1869	500 mm	1 inch	Common path
Defromable mirror	ALPAO 97-15	-	13.5 mm	Common path
Singlet	Thorlabs - LB1779	300 mm	1 inch	DNU SH-WFS path

We calibrated the system in order to have a 1:1 relation between the amplitude of the DM commands and the amplitudes of the modes calculated by interferometer. After this calibration the aberrations introduced on the DM can be measured simultaneously by the DNU SH-WFS and by the interferometer.

We used the interferometer as the source and as the truth wavefront sensor. Our goal was to compare the amplitude retrieved from the DNU SH-WFS measurements and the one measured by the interferometer for the injected one. The main goal is to evaluate if the DNU SH-WFS is able to measure and therefore estimate a phase variation equivalent to that of 20 nm. We injected ± 100 nm amplitude with 20 nm steps for the first 16 Zernike modes in open loop. Note that the DNU SH-WFS will be used in open loop during the nominal operations on MAVIS. During this test, we also check the linearity of the SH-WFS slopes. An example of the DNU SH-WFS slope linearity is shown in Fig. 7. The slopes show a linear behaviour inside the range of our measurements.

Taking as a reference Fig. 8: for the defocus the maximum deviation from the true injected amplitude is of -8.2 nm for -100 nm of injected amplitude and for the Vertical Secondary Astigmatism it is -5.1 nm; while the minimum deviations are -1.4 nm and -0.8 nm for -20 nm respectively. We noticed this trend for all the modes, but this could be expected and that is probably due to the hysteresis of the DM actuators and on the way on how we commanded the DM between the different steps. At each step, we took a reference measurement of the flat shape of the DM. This probably can also explain the linear trend for the DNU SH-WFS in Fig 8. The amplitudes calculated by the DNU SH-WFS differ on average by 6% from the true injected amplitudes taking into account all steps and all modes tested.

Figure 6. Left: linearity behaviour of the applied DM commands for the Defocus mode, on the x axis the amplitudes injected on the DM, on the y axis the amplitudes recorded by the interferometer. The amplitudes range is from -150 nm to 150 nm, the step is 15 nm. Right: the wavefront error shape on the interferometer for +150 nm and for -150 nm.

Figure 7. Left: the y axis shows the amplitudes calculated from the DNU SH WFS for the Vertical Secondary Astigmatism. The X axis shows the Zernike modes. The different colors show the injected amplitudes at the different steps. Left: slope X linearity for the Vertical Secondary Astigmatism. X axis shows injected amplitudes, Y axis shows the X slope rms values at each steps calculated as the difference in px from the spot reference positions of each sub-aperture of the DNU SH WFS.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we focussed on the DNU SH-WFS of MAVIS. We assembled and aligned its components: an off-the-shelf camera and an off-the-shelf MLA. We confirmed that is possible to mount and to align the camera and the MLA and to repeat the operations in the future with no showstoppers with respect to the nominal design.

The goal of the work was the characterization of the performance of the DNU SH-WFS and in particular we wanted to check that we were able to detect phase variations of 20 nm. To perform these tests we used a bench equipped with a 4D interferometer and an ALPAO 97-15 DM. To control the DM and to acquire data we used the DAO4MATTO control interface (based on the DAO RTC toolkit).

The DNU SH WFS slopes showed a linear behaviour inside the amplitudes range we chose and in addition we were able to detect amplitude variations of 20 nm. We notice that the variations from the injected amplitudes is bigger for bigger injected amplitudes. This trend is possibly due to the hysteresis and on how we commanded the DM between the different steps.

Figure 8. Difference between the injected amplitudes and the calculated amplitudes for the DNU SHWFS (black dots) and the 4D interferometer (red dots) for the Defocus on the left and for the Vertical secondary Astigmatism on the right.

In the near future our goal is to test the full dynamic range of the DNU SH WFS in open loop considering single modes and linear combinations of them and possibly to test the system with smaller phase variations.

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